

**Lea Weiß / Laura von Welzeck / Malte Vogl / Marten Düring / Aleksandra
Kaye / Jascha Schmitz / Raphael Schlattmann / Bernardo S. Buarque**

**Past, Present, and Future of HNR: Reflections on the Practices and Methods
in Historical Network Research Based on an Online Survey**

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Questionnaire

**Survey “Best-Practices and Tools in Historical Network Research”
(LimeSurvey, 21 September 2022 to 30 November 2022)**

Keywords

HNR community, HNR methods, network analysis, research practices, historical
network data

Title page: “Best-Practices and Tools in Historical Network Research”

Best-Practices and Tools in Historical Network Research

Dear member of the HNR community,

as researchers working on the analysis of historical networks, we share common tools and best-practices but also face similar questions and challenges. With this survey we would like to learn more about your views on these tools, practices, questions and challenges with the explicit goal to inform the development of future research software and educational resources.

The survey was developed as a collaboration between the ModelSEN project and the HNR community.

Contributors are

- Aline Deicke (Academy of Sciences and Literature, Mainz)
- Marten Düring (C2DH University of Luxembourg)
- Ingeborg van Vugt (University of Utrecht)
- Bernardo S. Buarque, Roberto Lalli, Malte Vogl, Lea Weiß, Dirk Wintergrün (Max Planck Institute for the History of Science, Berlin)

We plan to publish our findings upon completion.

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There are 61 questions in this survey.

A few questions on your academic profile

Your answers will help us to understand the link between academic profiles and research practices.

In which country do you currently work?

[selection from a list of countries / other (text)]

Please choose your current position / your highest academic degree.

[options: Bachelor, Master, PhD student, Doctoral degree, PostDoc, Senior researcher, Assistant professor, Professor, Librarian, Software engineer, Outside academia / other (text)]

For how many years have you been working with network-related methods?

(answer in years)

[number]

What is your disciplinary background (e.g. History, Sociology, Physics, ...)?

[text]

Concepts and methods from which fields do you use in your work?

[options: Scientometrics, Social network analysis, Complex systems dynamics / other (text)]

On what historical periods are your projects focused?

[options: Prehistory, Ancient history, Medieval period, Early modern period, Late modern period, Contemporary / other (text)]

Are you working with partners from other academic disciplines on the topic of networks or with network analysis methods?

[yes / no]

How often do you exchange knowledge and ideas with colleagues from other academic disciplines? (1: never / 2 / 3: occasionally / 4 / 5: regularly)

[options: Mathematics, Physics, Computer science, History, Social science, Information science, Design, Digital humanities, Other humanities, Libraries]

Tell us about your research projects!

Here we ask you about your methodological approach to network analysis in your current research projects. Please answer for a specific project you have been working on. Below you will have the option to add information for two additional projects.

Please give a brief outline (250 words max) of your research interest in your network-related project.

[free text]

Why do you use network analysis in your research? (1: not important, 2, 3: important, 4, 5: very important)

[options: I want to see the most relevant nodes in my network, I want to understand clusters of nodes, I want to understand the influence of the type or strength of connection, I want to understand structural changes in time, I want to understand attribute changes in time, I want to find missing information (e.g. structural holes), I want to understand the quality of my data, I want to understand the structural properties of a graph]

Which types of nodes do you work with?

[options: one type (unipartite), two types (bipartite), multiple different types]

Of what types are your nodes?

[options: Persons, Objects, Concepts, Places, Complex/mixed (e.g. hypernodes) / other (text)]

Which types of edges do you work with?

[options: one type only, several different types.]

Of what types are your edges?

[options: Social relations, Acts of communication, References, Co-occurrence, Complex/mixed (e.g. hyperedges) / other (text)]

Please describe your network, its nodes and their edges in a few sentences.

[free text]

Would you like to add another project?

[yes / no]

What standards and tools play a role in your projects?

Which formats do you use to store network data in your research projects?

[options: Excel, CSV, Pajek, GraphML, Ncol, Semantic net (OWL, RDF), JSON, GML / other (text)]

Do you use norm data (such as VIAF or Wikidata)?

[yes / no]

What kind of norm data do you use mostly for: persons, institutions, places, objects / artifacts

[options: GND, VIAF, Wikidata, GRID, ROR, Geonames, Pelagios, Other]

Do you also use other more specialized norm data? E.g. Getty Thesaurus, Iconclass, ...

[free text]

If you have a database to store your data, do you yourself have a data model or an ontology to organize this data?

[yes / no]

What standards and tools do you use to construct your ontology or data model?
[options: CIDOC-CRM, OWL, RDF, Triple store, Graph database, Neo4j / other (text)]

Please give a short description of the methods and tools you use to construct your ontology or data model, if needed.
[free text]

In your opinion, how important are ontologies for your research projects? What experiences can you share on working with ontologies? E.g. are you using existing ones?
[free text]

What programming languages do you use if any?
[options: R, Python, C, Javascript, None / other (text)]

What methods for network analysis do you know or use? (I know, but don't use: / I use:)
[options: Community detection algorithms (e.g. density-based clustering, random walker approaches), Positional analysis (e.g. blockmodeling, structural equivalence), Exponential Random Graph Model, Stochastic approaches for dynamic networks (e.g. RSiena), Centrality measures (e.g. betweenness centrality)]

Did we miss an important method in that list? Which one?
[free text]

What data visualization tools do you use?
[options: Gephi, Visone, VOSViewer, GraphViz / other (text)]

What other tools for network analysis do you use, that have not yet been mentioned?
[free text]

Have you ever published your data or methods using open standards?
[yes / no]

What percentage of your project time did you invest to reach that publication?
[number]

What was your experience with that publishing process? Were you able to follow established best-practices?
[free text]

In case you published your data/methods with open standards in the future, how much project time (in %) would you be willing to invest?
[number]

Have you ever published your code online? (E.g. using Git or Jupyter Notebooks)
[yes / no]

Developers of future research software for network analysis should focus on tools and methods for: (1: not important, 2, 3: important, 4, 5: very important)
[options: Data organization & ontology modeling, Data cleaning, Linking to norm data, Sharing data, Accessing repositories, Other aspects]

What other aspects would you like to mention?
[free text]

What other digital methods (e.g. databases, visualisation tools) do you use, if any?
[free text]

Some questions on the role of network research and the HNR community

Generally speaking, what is the function of network research in your research projects? (1: not important, 2, 3: important, 4, 5: very important)
[options: Testing historical arguments, Data cleaning, Heuristics to find missing data, Heuristics to generate new hypotheses about structural relations, Other]

What other function does network analysis have for you?

[free text]

What are in your opinion the largest difficulties you face in your research process with networks?

[free text]

Are you already involved (e.g. event participation, contributions, ...) with the Historical Network Research community?

[options: Yes, No, I would like to get involved]

What type of HNR activity do you consider most important for your research? (1: not important, 2, 3: important, 4, 5: very important)

[options: HNR Lunch Lecture, HNR Workshop Series, HNR Conference, HNR Bibliography, HNR Newsletter, Journal of Historical Network Research]

How would you like to benefit from the Historical Network Research community in the future? (1: not important, 2, 3: important, 4, 5: very important)

[options: Stay informed about ongoing research in the field, Support with methodological questions, Communication of failure or null results, Critical reflection of methods, Interdisciplinary exchange, Common tool development, Development of standards for HNR, Data sharing]

I would be willing to play an active role in the HNR community. Please feel free to contact me:

[free text]

What aspects are you missing in the HNR community?

[free text]

Which important question did we not ask you? Do you have any comments for us?

[free text]